

Gibbs' Paradox, Indistinguishability and Local Pressure Part III

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In Parts I and II, we argued that the indistinguishability of particles of a classical statistical mechanical gas (e.g. a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas) follows from pressure balance which creates the equilibrium. In other words, pressure is the physical driving force for balance and it does not matter whether particle 1 is at r_1 and particle 2 at r_2 or vice versa if they have the same momentum (energy). As a result, in Part II we suggested finding particle parameters which pertain to a momentum balance, i.e. the spatial density, velocity of a particle, momentum and remove all unnecessary information associated with these parameters. Given that one has spatial density as a quantity of interest, one sees that this is not a particle property. The position of a particle is one of its properties, but one must be careful to retain the sense of spatial density. As a result, if one characterizes a particle by position and energy, then interchanging two particles with the same energy does not create a new state. One is interested in counting states because in order to minimize information, one must maximize the number of states, described by parameters pertinent to pressure balance. As a result, one uses $1/n(e)!$ in the expression: $N! / \text{Product over } e_i n(e_i)!$. As a result, we argued that indistinguishability is due to pressure and does not have a quantum origin, but is rather due to pressure balance which requires density.

This leads to the question: What does one do in quantum mechanics? Quantum mechanics is said to be a statistical theory with a particle being described by an energy eigenfunction for example. If one has several particles in a potential well, one may create a product wavefunction $W_1(r_1)W_2(r_2)W_3(r_3)$. Here r_1 is the position of particle 1, but W_1 represents the first energy level. Quantum mechanics is not derived using pressure balance, but nonrelativistic energy eigenfunctions follow from the time independent Schrodinger equation. As a result, one might think that the $1/N!$ requirement is not needed. We argue, however, that quantum solutions are very much of the nature of an equilibrium situation because tails of wavefunctions existing outside of classical turning points represent tunneling into and out of a bound region. As a result, we argue that a $1/N!$ pressure related feature be kept because physically changing the particle identities associated with certain fixed energy eigenstates does not change physical properties associated with an equilibrium. Quantum mechanical solutions, however, do not follow from maximizing entropy, but rather from the Schrodinger equation. We suggest, however, that for more than one particle, one consider permutations of the coordinates in A . Given that the density is of the form W^*W , W or $-W$ yield the same density. Thus, we suggest that a combination of A 's with permuted coordinates should be yield either a factor of 1 or -1 upon interchange of any two coordinates. The wavefunction also has the normalization factor $1/\sqrt{N!}$ where N is the number of particles. Thus, the density again uses the $1/N!$ result associated with pressure not depending on the actual position of a particle if it does not change the pressure. For permutations of position in A , the pressure is the same. As a result, we argue that the $1/N!$ In quantum mechanical density is consistent with the pressure balance equilibrium picture of classical physics.

Classical Statistical Mechanics and Pressure Balance

We argue that a balance of pressure in a classical gas is key to establishing equilibrium. This, however, does not yield $P(e_i)$, a distribution of single particle energies, although it does yield a constant spatial density, if $P(e_i)$ is the same at each r point. In order to find the exact form of $P(e_i)$, we suggested in Part II that one first find the pertinent particle parameters associated with pressure balance and then remove all unnecessary information. This is equivalent to maximizing the number of states defined by these parameters. For a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, this is a little tricky because it is spatial density and particle energy which are important. If particle 1 with energy e_1 and is at r_1 and particle 2 with energy e_2 is at r_2 , one has the same pressure if one switches particles. Thus, there is a sense of indistinguishability, due to pressure, which must be accounted for in an

extremization process. This leads to the factor $1/n(e_i)!$ in $N! / \text{Product } n(e_i)!$. Extremizing with respect to $n(e_i)$ and using the constraint $E_{\text{ave}} = \sum_i e_i P(e_i)$ yields the MB distribution. The above argument for the presence of $1/n(e_i)!$ does not depend on quantum mechanics. Furthermore, it is a condition introduced when creating a function, called entropy, which is to be extremized? What does one do in quantum mechanics?

Quantum Mechanics

Quantum mechanics is a statistical theory, but it is based, in the nonrelativistic case, on the solution of a Schrodinger equation which is of the form of an energy conservation equation with average kinetic energy given by:

$$KE_{\text{ave}} = \left(\sum_p p^2/2m a(p) \exp(ipx) \right) / \left(\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \right) \quad ((1))$$

There is no explicit extremization of entropy, nor is there is explicit pressure balance. As a result, quantum mechanics may appear, at first glance, not to be like the equilibrium picture of classical mechanics. We argue, however, that there is a very close connection. First of all we point out the similarity:

$$\exp(-e_1/T) \exp(-e_2/T) = \exp(- (e_1+e_2)/T) \quad ((2))$$

((2)) is a property of the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. This distribution may be obtained by extremizing entropy subject to an average energy constraint, as discussed above.

In quantum mechanics, one has:

$$\exp(ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x) \quad ((3))$$

In previous notes, we have argued that this similarity suggests that $\exp(ipx)$ is the solution of a maximization of entropy $-P(px) \ln(P(px))$ subject to the complex constraint $ipxP(px)$. This yields a kind of probability form for a free particle.

To deal with a single bound particle in a potential $V(x)$, one needs to introduce an average conservation of energy equation, i.e. the time independent Schrodinger equation. Thus, even dealing with a single particle in a potential $V(x)$, it appears that there is no extremization of entropy, while $\exp(ipx)$ follows from entropy extremization. We argue, however, that the time independent Schrodinger equation yields energy eigenvalue solutions which are very much of an equilibrium type nature as there is tunneling in and out of the bound state region. Thus, we argue that to a certain degree, there is a similarity between classical statistical mechanics and the quantum single particle solution.

A major difference, however, is that the classical scenario begins with many particles (i.e. Stirling's approximation is often cited in the literature when obtaining the MB distribution), while a quantum free particle and a solution of the Schrodinger time independent equation only involve one particle. This is not to say that one cannot consider multiple particles in different energy eigenstates in a potential $V(x)$. In such a case, one might consider the expression:

$$W = W_1(x_1) W_2(x_2) W_3(x_3) \text{ for } N=3 \quad ((4))$$

Here W_i represents the i th energy eigenstate and x_i represents particle i 's position. One may consider permuting x_i values, just as one may interchange particles in the classical scenario. If one does not change the energy states, but shifts the particle identity, one does not obtain a new state with respect to pressure, as argued in the classical situation. We argue that the same result holds in the quantum case as we argue that a quantum bound state is very much an equilibrium one. Given

that spatial density in quantum mechanics is:

spatial density = $W^* W$ (one may integrate out all but one variable) ((5))

it seems that W may be +/- on the interchange of two particle identities. This leads to creating symmetric and antisymmetric combinations of ((4)) with the normalization constant $1/\sqrt{n!}$, because there are $n!$ ways to permute n particle identities (i.e. n consecutive numbers). For the density form ((5)) becomes $1/n!$, where n is the number of particles. Thus, the $1/n!$ term, based on pressure not depending on particle identity, appears again. In other words, we argue that the nature of pressure or equilibrium not based on particle identity enforces particle indistinguishability in both the classical and quantum cases.

Boson and Fermion Features

The unique quantum result that one have plus/minus one when one interchanges particle identities for a fixed set of eigenfunctions leads to symmetric and antisymmetric wavefunctions. For two particles, an antisymmetric result is one for which one cannot have two particles in the same energy eigenstate. A symmetric wavefunction is one for which one may have multiple particles in the same energy eigenstate. For a collision problem, an antisymmetric situation means that if two particles with e_1 and e_2 collide, one may only obtain e_3 and e_4 ($e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$) if e_3 and e_4 are not occupied by another particle.

The boson (symmetric) case seems to be a little more confusing. If one only considers single particle properties, then classically one has a particle with e_1 strike a particle with e_2 at a specific point. Quantum mechanics, however, deals with wavefunctions which are statistical, equilibrium type solutions even for a single particle, as argued above. Thus, an energy eigenfunction for e_i does not represent a particle with energy e_i at a point. If one has several particles and a symmetric wavefunction with the normalization constant $1/\sqrt{n!}$, then this is a statistical representation of an equilibrium scenario, and not a single particle picture. We argued classically, that one introduces $1/n(e_i)! j_n$ in a classical gas because pressure balance does not depend on the identity of the particle with certain e_i , but the e_i 's. If one tries, however, to interpret the symmetric wavefunction in a single particle manner, then it has the following unusual interpretation. One may consider n particles in the same e_i state. If particles are indistinguishable due to the pressure balance argument, and if one particle comes out, then there is an enhanced probability of n because one does not know which one came out. The indistinguishability, however, is a consequence of pressure balance and so one is not really dealing with a single particle, but with a pressure balance situation which includes the various particle identity interchange terms with the normalization factor $1/\sqrt{n!}$. If there is an enhanced probability for a single particle (in this mapping to a single particle picture), then the same should hold for scattering into the state e_i . This then is the boson enhancement factor. The above argument is very similar to that given by Feynman in his Lecture Notes (1). What makes the argument a little confusing, we suggest, is that one tries to map the statistical equilibrium situation (which argue is what even a single particle wavefunction represents) which does not depend on particle identity into a picture of a single particle scattering into a state e_i with n particles. In such a case, the single particle has an identity, but the problem is ultimately solved assuming no particle identity and this has the consequence of the boson enhancement factor, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in the classical statistical mechanical case, pressure balance is key to equilibrium. In Part 1, we suggested that a classical gas could be described by particle parameters linked to pressure balance. The pressure of a one dimensional gas particle is based on v and p , or $e=pp/2m$, but also on spatial density, if the average particle pressure is the same at each spatial point. Spatial density is not a particle property, but is related to the position of a particle. One may,

however, interchange the identity of all particles if the energy states don't change and this does not lead to an extra macrostate when trying to eliminate all possible information, maximize the number of macrostates. Thus, we argued in Part I that the nature of pressure leads to the $1/n(e_i)!$ factor in the Number of states expression: $N! / \text{Product over } e_i n(e_i)!$. This is a purely classical feature, so what happens in the case of quantum mechanics?

Here we argue that quantum mechanics is also based on a maximization of entropy, but this occurs for a free particle, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ is of a similar form to the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor $C \exp(-e_i/T)$. We have suggested in previous notes that $\exp(ipx)$ is the solution of a maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to a $\sum p(x) = 1$ constraint. If a single particle is placed in a potential well, then one has conservation of average energy and this leads to the time independent Schrodinger equation with energy eigenfunction solutions. We argue that these are very much of an equilibrium nature as tunneling in and out of the bound region is included. In other words, some features of a many particle classical statistical mechanical problem appear for a single quantum particle. We thus argue that if one has several quantum particles occupying different energy eigenstates, for example, that one may consider a sum of terms involving all possible interchanges of particle identities, but this should yield the same overall expression or one with a minus sign, because spatial density is W^*W . The number of interchanges in $n!$, so W should have a normalization of $1/\sqrt{n!}$. In other words, the overall W includes all possible identity permutations divided by $1/\sqrt{n!}$ and so again there is particle indistinguishability, which we argue is again due to the nature of an equilibrium balance situation (similar to classical pressure balance) as we argue that the quantum equilibrium situation is an equilibrium one for which the interchange of particle identities for the same set of states does not change the physical nature of the situation.

The plus/minus factor which appears on interchanging particle identities in the wavefunction has interesting consequences. In the symmetric (plus or boson) case, one really deals with wavefunctions which are not the same as a single particle scattering into a state e_i with n particles. If one tries to pretend that one has a single particle at a point x , then the symmetric picture of indistinguishable particles (because equilibrium balance does not depend on particle identity) means that if one had n particles in e_i and one comes out, there is an enhancement of a factor n in probability. This, however, is due to a statistical picture of the problem which imposes particle indistinguishability as a feature of equilibrium balance.

References

1. Feynman, R. Lecture Notes [The Feynman Lectures on Physics \(caltech.edu\)](http://www.caltech.edu/~leighton/feynman/)